

ISic0510

I.Sicily inscription 0510

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.11.12 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo Civico di
Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491735

EDCS 22000816

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7230 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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IN HOC MONUMENTO
REQUIESCIT CORPUS
BEATISSIMI PATRIS
MAGISTRI VALENTINI
DE MONTI S. MARCI
CIVIS ROMANI
QUI OBIT DIE 10
MAY 1600 AETATIS
SUAE 72 ANNI
ET 6 MENSIVUS
ET 15 DIEBUS
IN AETATE SUAE
SINGULARI
VIRI
SAPIENTISSIMI
ET
PIISSIMI

Photo M. Metcalfe